
CORPORATE CASH HOLDING AND FIRM CHARACTERISTICS: EVIDENCE FROM NIGERIA'S IN AGRICULTURAL AND CONSUMER GOODS SECTORS

¹Ugwu, Timothy Chidubem and ²Ugwueze, Amaka Catherine

¹School of Business and Management Technology, Federal Polytechnic Ohodo, Enugu State.

²Department of Accountancy Enugu State University of Science and Technology, Enugu State.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15260220>

Abstract: This work examined corporate cash holding and firm characteristics: evidence from Nigeria's in agricultural and consumer goods sectors. The study was necessitated by the inability of some agricultural and consumer goods firms to take up expansionary opportunities without debt. Profit for the year (PFTY), and capital expenditure (CEXP), were used as proxies for firm's characteristics being the independent variable, while cash holding was used as the dependent variable and was proxies by cash and cash equivalents (CCE). All the five agricultural companies and fourteen consumer goods companies listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX) as at the last working day of December, 2021 were selected using stratified sampling technique. *Ex-Post facto* research design was adopted. The study covered the period 2011-2021. Five hypotheses were formulated and tested using random panel regression output aided by E-views 9.0. Finding reveal that PFTY has positive and significant effect on CCE($r= 0.61346$; $P = 0.0052 < 0.05$; $t = 3.407741 > 2.0$). This implies that as firms make more profits, the likelihood of having more cash holdings increases. CEXP has positive and significant effect on CCE ($r = 0.115649$; $P = 0.0453 < 0.05$; $t = 2.719229 > 2.0$). The implication is that an increase in CEXP will lead to increase in cash holding. The study concludes that PFTY, and CEXP, have positive and significant effect on CCE. Recommendations include taking up aggressive marketing and promotion as well as increased sales; thorough evaluation of capital expenditure, while strategic mergers and acquisition, and strategic investment in new and improved technology should be considered. Management should seek cheaper sources of funding to reduce the burden of servicing debt.

Keywords: Firm's characteristics, corporate cash holding, Profit for the year, Capital Expenditure

1.1 Introduction

Cash is one of the most important factors that determine whether firms will be able to settle creditors and other suppliers, pay salaries and meet other short term and long term obligations as they fall due and as well take advantage of opportunities that location, seasons and circumstances provide. Cash is a current asset. It comprises currency notes, coins and currency equivalents that can be accessed on the immediate or almost immediately, hence the importance of cash and cash equivalents to firms in all the sectors of the economy, most especially in the agricultural and consumer goodssector in Nigeria. In their view, Ugwu, Ugwu and Uzoma (2021) opine that it is ideal for firms to prioritize cash management otherwise known as liquidity management in order to hold optimal cash level. This will help them to face the challenges of expanding value chain, tech-increase, and acquisition of improved input materials and meet short term and long term obligations as they fall

due. This explains why the discussion on cash holding is a focal point on accounting and corporate finance literatures. Ogundipe, Ogundipe and Ajao (2012) describe cash holding as cash and cash equivalent that can easily be converted into cash. In other words, cash holding includes cash and all the near cash items or investments whose maturity duration falls between 90 days to 180 days.

Cash equivalents are those current assets that are quickly convertible to cash for investment purposes and to off-set current liabilities. This requires strategic planning. Firms set target cash level and cash are usually held at the target level with the desired benefits of cash holding in focus. Firms hold cash to provide for, and be able to meet obligations as soon they fall due. According to Opler, Pinkowitz, Stulz and Williamson (1999), it is a strategic financial management effort that is usually aligned with a set objective, irrespective of size of firm. One of the objectives of firms is to keep investing especially when it is desirable. It is mostly top on the agenda of any management to keep taking advantage of opportunities even when cash flow is at all-time low in relation to investment cash requirement and when borrowing cost is high, hence planning of cash holding remains critical and firm managers must pay necessary attentions to the cost that accompany holding cash. It is advised that the benefit of cash held should at least off-set the cost of holding it for optimality of result. Kinnunen (2015) opines that managers have

concerned themselves with finding an optimal level of cash to hold. There are costs associated with holding cash and its equivalents, such as tax costs and lower rate of return. It is also important to note that cash is often a vital component of a firm's business strategy as it represents the most liquid asset that firms can easily dispose of. The outcome of a trade-off between costs and benefits of holding cash or liquid assets could be seen as the firm's optimum cash holding level of agricultural and consumer goods firms. As such, cash aids the financing of new business ideas and investments. Cash enhances the ability of agricultural and consumer goods companies to meet both their short term and long term obligations. With a good cash holding policy, corporate bodies in agricultural and consumer goods sectors should be able to engage in capital expenditure that is capable of multiplying value chain, increase firm size, enhance improved revenue generation and earn more profits.

In their view, Boubaker, Derouiche and Nguyen (2015) opine that cash reserves could be seen as the assurances for financial independence of organizations which empowers them to follow-through their strategic plans without external interference. With cash availability, agricultural and consumer goods firms could easily venture into newly found value chains, provide inputs and procure machineries, etc., which should impart the firm size considerably. Increase in value chains brings about expansion of, or increase in assets. This affects the firm size considerably. Boubaker, et al, (2015) opines that there is a direct relationship between firm size and firm profitability. It is instructive to note that the more profit a firm generates the more reserves or funds are available for short term and long term investment purposes. Additionally, internally generated funds are cheaper and quicker to access than those externally sourced. As a result, firms with sufficient cash reserves can explore prospective investment opportunities at a lower cost of financing. However, stock piling cash reserves might inadvertently fuel agency problems or goal incongruence in the use of corporate resources (Tang, Subramaniam, Zhou & Hue, 2011). More so, Ali and Yousaf (2013) argue that

sufficient liquid assets afford managers the flexibility to deploy resources even to projects with negative net present value (NPV).

It becomes imperative to emphasize that cash holdings have both positive side which should be maximized and negative side which should be curtailed.

Despite these reports, it is emphasized that maintaining optimum cash holding remains a necessity hence, efforts have been in place to identify the effect of cash holding in relation to firm's characteristics such as profitability, capital expenditure, firm size and leverage, as well as growth opportunities, cashflow, dividend payout, account receivable and payables, etc. Although the discussion on cash holdings trend is not limited to the US economy, there are just few numbers of research has been conducted in Asian and African countries such as Nigeria. This call for concern in this part of the world hence, this study seeks to examine the effect of firm characteristics on corporate cash holdings of agricultural and consumer goods sectors in Nigeria.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Ideally, investors and managers of companies make various financial decisions in order to remain in operation. Organizations make right choices to maintain good working capital which allows them to source for inputs, meet short term and long-term obligation, achieve optimum profitability and take advantage of new business expansionary opportunities at the lowest cost possible without high debt profile. These points underscore the need to maintain optimum cash holding always.

However, concerted efforts of the government, financing and donor bodies on the stimulation of investor interest towards investment, development and growth of agricultural and consumer goods sectors notwithstanding, poor performance, slow development and low interest of investors as well as inability of some agricultural and consumer goods firms to take advantage of expansionary opportunities in the sector has continued unabated. Leverage (debt profile) of agricultural and consumer goods firms continues to rise at the detriment of profit which could be the reason profitability of the few players in the sector still looks unattractive when compared with some other sectors. This could have a far-reaching effect on the cash holding problems that agricultural and consumer goods firms in Nigeria battle with. As a result, it has become imperative to figure out how firm characteristics affect corporate cash holding.

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Although many researchers have studied the effect of firm characteristics on corporate cash holding of different sectors in many countries, none has delved into such with focus on the agricultural and consumer goods sectors, not even on the Nigerian geographical location. Meanwhile, it is expected that increase in profit should trigger increase on the capital expenditure with a positive effect on firm size; a situation that should attract more investors in the sector. It is also expected to keep the cash holding on the upward trajectory thereby reducing the rate of borrowings by agricultural and consumer goods firms. However, the sector has continued to make relatively low profit when compared with other sectors, hence little or no cash holding as could be seen through borrowing activities of the firms on the sector. Investor interests are still being stimulated through numerous government supports funding and low cost of funding but leverage of firms in the sector has remained high with low expansionary efforts by the very few players in the sector. This calls for concern. Hence, this work

examined the effect of firm characteristics such as profitability, capital expenditure, leverage and firm size on corporate cash holding of agricultural and consumer goods sectors in Nigeria with a view to knowing how firm characteristics affect cash holding and the implications on the firms.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

The general objective of the study was to examine the Corporate cash holding and firm characteristics: evidence from Nigeria's in agricultural and consumer goods sectors, while the specific objectives of the study was to;

- i. determine the effect of profit for the year on cash and cash equivalents.
- ii. ascertain the effect of capital expenditure on cash and cash equivalents.

1.4 Research Questions

To achieve the stated objective, the following research questions were formulated to guide the study;

- i. What is the effect of profit for the year on cash and cash equivalents of firms in agricultural and consumer goods sectors in Nigeria?
- ii. To what extent does capital expenditure affect cash and cash equivalents of firms in agricultural and consumer goods sectors in Nigeria?

1.5 Statement of Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study and were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

- i. Profit for the year does not have significant effect on cash and cash equivalents of firms in agricultural and consumer goods sectors in Nigeria.
- ii. Capital expenditure does not have significant effect on cash and cash equivalents of firms in agricultural and consumer goods sectors in Nigeria.

Review of Related Literature

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Firm's Characteristics

This refers to the attributes that make up the firm characteristics. For the purpose of this study, the characteristics considered which guided the study are: Profitability; Capital Expenditure; Firm Size, Leverage and Asset Structure. Firm characteristics refer to the attributes which a particular firm possesses that defines its activities. Firm characteristics are those variables that relatively affect the firm's decision both internally and externally (Shehu, 2012). It is described as a firm's demographic and managerial variables which, in turn, comprise part of the firm's internal environment. According to Kogan and Tian (2012), firm characteristics include firm size, leverage, liquidity, sales growth, asset growth and turnover. Others include ownership structure, board characteristics, age of the firm, dividend pay-out, profitability, access to capital markets and growth opportunities (McKnight & Weir, 2018):

2.1.1.1 Profitability

Profitability refers to ability to make profit from business activities of an organization, company, firm, or an enterprise Pandey (2002). It shows how efficiently the management can make profit by using all the resources available in the market. Profitability is an index of efficiency; and is regarded as a measure of efficiency and management guide to greater efficiency, Edom, Inah and Adanma (2015). Though, profitability is an important yardstick for measuring the efficiency, the extent of profitability cannot be taken as a final proof of efficiency.

Various decision tools or profitability ratios can be employed to evaluate an organization's profitability. Murthy (1978) opines that "the most important measurement of profitability of a company is ratio. Some of the tools are: profit margin, return on assets (ROA), and return on equity (ROE). Profitability is always the core reason behind the existence of a company. For many businesses it still is. There is no way that businesses could continue to exist without generating adequate profits. Only government companies could continue to make losses in the long run. As far as private companies are concerned, the moment they start making losses, they are on probation. They have to turn around the business to become profitable with immediate effect or lose investor funding (MSG, 2021).

2.1.1.2 Capital Expenditure

Capital expenditures refer to funds that are used by a company for the purchase, improvement, or maintenance of long-term assets. Long term assets are assets that a company uses in its production process and with a useful life of more than one year. Such assets are also to improve the efficiency or capacity of the company. Long-term assets are usually physical, fixed and non-consumable. Tangible assets are assets with a physical form and that hold value. Examples include property, plant, and equipment. Tangible assets are such as property, equipment, or infrastructure and that have a useful life of more than one accounting period. There are normally two forms of capital expenditures: (1) expenses to maintain levels of operation present within the company and (2) expenses that will enable an increase in future growth. A capital expense can either be tangible, such as a machine, or intangible, such as a patent. Both intangible and tangible capital expenditures are usually considered assets since they can be sold when there is a need. It is important to note that funds spent on repair or in conducting continuing, normal maintenance on assets is not considered capital expenditure and should be expensed on the income statement. The Income Statement is one of a company's core financial statements that show their profit and loss over a period of time. The profit or whenever it is incurred as repair and maintenance expense (Moeen, Zeeshan, Qasim, Zain & Zoya, 2021).

2.1.2 Cash holding

Corporate cash holding is a strategy of corporate financial management, which not only relates to corporate operation development, governance and institutional environment. Gill and Shah (2012) defined cash holding as cash in hand or cash available for investment in physical assets and to distribute to investors. Cash holding is hence viewed as cash or cash equivalent that is easily converted into cash. Holding cash is at a cost, which is the opportunity cost of the capital invested in liquid assets. The potential profit forgone on holding large cash balance is an opportunity cost to the firm. There are benefits proving that cash holding is valuable to firms and its shareholders. According to Ferreira and Vilela (2004) the benefits of cash holding are:

- i) Reduction in the likelihood of financial distress,
- ii) Allowing the pursuance of investment policy when financial constraints are met, and
- iii) Minimizing the costs of raising external funds or liquidating existing assets.

2.2 Theoretical Review

The study was anchored on Pecking Order Theory propounded by Myers and Majluf in 1984 postulate that financing comes from three sources, internal funds, debt and new equity and suggests that companies

prioritize their sources of financing, first preferring internal financing, and then debt, lastly raising equity as a last resort.

This theory assumes that a business leader complies with the following hierarchy: self-financing, non-risky debt issuance, risky debt issuance and equity issuance as a last resort. Such behaviour eschews a fall in the prices of shares of the firm; it restricts the distribution of dividends in order to increase cash flow and reduces the cost of capital by limiting as much as possible access to loans. Thus, profitable firms enjoy more internal funds available. Pecking order theory (or pecking order model) postulates that the cost of financing increases with asymmetric information. Financing comes from three sources, internal funds, debt and new equity. Companies prioritize their sources of financing, first preferring internal financing, and then debt, lastly raising equity as a “last resort

Company managers typically possess more information regarding the company’s performance, prospects, risks, and future outlook than external users such as creditors (debtholders) and investors (shareholder). Therefore, to compensate for information asymmetry, external users demand a higher return to counter the risk that they are taking. In essence, due to information asymmetry, external sources of finances demand a higher rate of return to compensate for risk. In the context of the pecking order theory, retained earnings financing (internal financing) comes directly from the company and minimizes information asymmetry. As opposed to external financing such as debt and equity financing where the company must incur fees to issue external financing, internal financing is the cheapest and most convenient source of financing.

2.3 Empirical Review

2.3.1 Profitability and Cash holding

Ham, Nguyen, & Nguyen, (2020) examined the influence of working capital management (WCM) factors on the profitability of steel companies listed on the Stock Exchange of Vietnam. Data was collected from audited financial statements of companies for a period of 10 years, from 2010 to 2019. The number of samples eligible for research was 20 out of 26 companies, which is equivalent to 76.9%. With the help of dedicated software STATA version 14, the impact determination of WCM (through 8 independent variables: DIO, DPO, DSO, CCC, SIZ, CR, LEV, GRO) to the firm's profitability (through the dependent variable) is performed through multivariate regression models. Research results from companies in the steel industry in Vietnam during this period indicate that WCM has a strong impact on the profitability of businesses. Among 8 factors affecting the profitability of steel enterprises, factors DPO, DIO, DSO, CR, SIZ, GRO have a positive impact, boosting profitability; 2 factors CCC and LEV have a negative impact on profitability; in which, the effect of CCC is negligible.

Abdul and Raj (2020) examined the impact of operating cash flows on the companies’ financial performance in the manufacturing and insurance sectors in Saudi Arabia listed on the Tadawul stock exchange during the period 2015–2018 for insurance companies, while it is 2014–2018 for manufacturing companies. The data were extracted from companies’ annual reports by considering Return on Assets (ROA) and Return on Equity (ROE) as dependent variables, CFOs as an explanatory variable, firm size (SIZE) and Leverage (LEV) as control variables, and an industry dummy. The study sample consisted of five (5) companies from each sector totaling 10. The sample size of the current study depends upon the availability of financial data. The data were collected

from companies' financial reports and were used to calculate different financial ratios employed as dependent and independent variables in the study. Descriptive statistics, correlation, pooled regression was adopted for empirical analysis. Further, the study conducted diagnostic tests, such as the test of normality, heteroscedasticity, multicollinearity, etc. to examine the robustness of the results. The results report a positive and significant association between financial performance (ROA and ROE) and operating cash flows (CFOs), and a negative association for SIZE and LEV. Therefore, the study concluded that the firms' operating cash flows in the insurance and manufacturing sectors in Saudi Arabia affect financial performance.

Davidson and Rosmita (2020) carried out a study to examine the influence of profitability, liquidity, firm size, and leverage towards cash holding in manufacturing companies listed on Indonesia Stock Exchange in period of 2016- 2018. The technique of sample selection is using purposive sampling method and the data source of the study was a secondary one and obtained a 74 sample manufacturing companies. The analytical method used in this research is a regression analysis of panel data with fixed effect model using E-Views software of version 10. The results of this research show that profitability, liquidity, and leverage have positive effect on cash holding but firm size has no effect on cash holding.

Pandey (2020) carried out a study to identify the impact of cash management on profitability. This study was adopted correlation research design. Purposive sampling method was adopted while undertaking research. 80 samples were considered while collecting data. The sample structure consisted of small and medium manufacturing businesses in the Kirtipur Municipality. Owners of such enterprises were taken as sample because they can better understand the cash management. Data were collected using five point Likert Scale Questionnaires. Data were analyzed using mean, correlation and regression models. Study found that Cash management has an insignificant but positive effect on profitability. It clarifies that conversion cycle, cash flow and inventory manage positively effects to the profitability but the effect is nominal.

Abudu, Yinping, Isaac and Alhassan (2021) empirically examined the impact of working capital management (WCM) on the profitability of Small and Medium Scale Enterprises (SMEs) in the context of a developing economy, Ghana. We analyzed data on 366 SMEs over a 10-year period, spanning 2007 to 2016. Generalized method of moment (GMM) estimation was employed. The data analyses are presented in three forms. First is the use of descriptive statistics. The second and third involved the use of pairwise correlation and ultimately the regression estimates. The results reveal a positive relationship between trade payable period and profitability. The inventory conversion period and cash conversion cycle show a negative association with profitability. The results show an inverted U-shaped relationship between trade receivables collection period and corporate profitability, an indication of an optimal trade receivables collection period that maximizes profitability. Further check suggests a deviation from the optimal trade receivables collection period significantly and negatively affects corporate profitability. The study revealed the need for firms to ensure efficient management of working capital to maximize profitability.

2.3.2 Capital expenditure and Cash holding

Kenny and Luqman (2019) examined the impact of firm's characteristics on the quality of financial reporting of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. Some 25 nonfinancial firms listed on the Nigeria stock exchange from 2009 to 2016 comprised the sample. The study used longitudinal balanced panel data from secondary sources

only because it is a quantitative with positivism paradigm and the core of the data needed for analysis were adequately and conveniently extracted from the audited financial reports of the selected firms within the study period. Multiple regression is adopted to examine the model of the study. Longitudinal panel data is used to account for individual heterogeneity of the sample companies with the utilization of two steps regression in determining the quality of financial reports of the Nigerian listed manufacturing firms adopting modified Dechow and Dichev's (2002) model. The firm characteristics are firm size, firm tangibility, profitability and growth. The result revealed that firm size has positive significant effect on financial reporting quality. Tangibility has negative significant effect on audit financial reporting quality. Firm's profitability has also been argued to have a positive influence on the quality of financial reporting while firm growth has negative significant effect on financial reporting quality. Hence large firms tend to produce high quality financial reports; this should be encouraged among firms. This study also revealed that highly profitable firms have high financial reporting.

Tahir, Sabir, Alam, & Ismail, (2019) conducted a study with an attempt to bridge the gap in the literature by offering empirical evidence about firm's characteristics and their effect to stock returns. The secondary data of 307 Non-financial companies listed in Karachi Stock Exchange (KSE) were collected from the B-Recorder and Basic Balance Sheet Analysis (BBA) issued by the State Bank Of Pakistan for the period from 2000 to 2012. Market Capitalization (MC), sales Growth (SG), Earnings per Share (EPS) and Book to Market value (BMV) were taken as independent variables while Stock Market Returns as dependent variable. First two independent variables were used as proxies for size effect while later as value effect. Economic techniques like Correlation Matrix, Multiple regression analysis, Unit root test and Granger Causality were applied for empirical testing of the data. Results revealed that MC, EPS and BTM value had significant impact while sales growth had no effect on stock market returns.

Samarajeewa, and Perera, (2020) carried out a study on the impact of capital expenditure on working capital management: Evidence from the Listed Manufacturing Companies in the Colombo Stock Exchange (CSE). The study investigated the effect of capital expenditure (CE) on working capital management (WCM) using quarterly financial data of 30 selected listed manufacturing companies in Sri Lanka during the period of 2014 to 2018. The Net liquidity balance (NLB), working capital requirement (WCR) and cash conversion cycle (CCC) were utilized as proxies for WCM and pooled least squares regression analysis model was used analyzing the relationship between CE and WCM. Based on three different models, six different hypotheses were tested. The effect of CE financial expenditure and operating expenditure on NLB were investigated as the first model and secondly the effect on WCR and CCC was investigated. The significant negative relationship has been identified between NLB and CE, which implies that these firms do not strive increasing the balance of most liquid assets when facing with CE since firms use debt or bank overdraft as firms don't have enough internally generated funds to be used in long term fixed investments. Further, the insignificant relationship between operating working capital and CE was found. Based on the investigation, managerial implications of the manufacturing companies have to consider the trend of CE in managing WC and establish trade between CE and WCM in order to enhance long term profitability through fixed asset investment while ensuring smooth functioning of company's liquidity activities without incurring any liquidity risk.

Thabiso and Celani, (2021) carried out a study to investigate the firm characteristics and drivers of financial performance using 121 publicly traded non-life insurance companies from 16 Southern African Development Community (SADC) countries during the period from 2008 to 2019. The consolidated least squares and two-step generalized method of moments estimators were used to analyze a panel data set of 1,452 observations. The findings show that a lagged return on assets, equity capital, operational efficiency, leverage and investment capability are statistically significant determinants of financial performance in non-life insurance companies of SADC countries, even though equity capital, operational efficiency, and leverage are inversely significant. The insurance industry, policymakers, the state, and shareholders should consider these important variables when making decisions, and enhance their performance according to the findings. It is also suggested that the industry's capital structures should be reformed to preserve a favorable balance of equity and debt amongst the businesses. Additionally, measures such as automated systems that may decrease operating costs should be used to improve financial performance.

Moeen, Zeeshan, Qasim, Zain and Zoya, (2021) investigated the relationship of cash flow, capital expenditures and financial leverage with performance of Pharmaceutical firms in Pakistan over the period 2009-2018. Random effect model is applied for empirical testing the relationship in a static model. The results disclose a significant nexus of cash flow, capital expenditures and financial leverage with the performance of Pharmaceutical firms. Keeping in view the hypothesis of study, the cash flow, capital expenditures and financial leverage are more likely results in higher performance of pharmaceutical firms. The study has significant implications for corporate managers, policy makers and investors. Previous studies have mostly used stock return volatility to measure the performance of firm. This study has focused on the other three variables to measure the performance of firms.

2.4 Gap in Empirical Literature

The researches as summarized above were mostly carried out in sectors and areas like accommodation industry; banking sector, manufacturing sector, food and beverage industry, industrial goods sector, united economies and emerging markets, etc. As observed from the above summary table, there are just a few searches that have been conducted in Nigeria in relation to firm characteristics and corporate cash holding. However, worthy of note from the empirical reviews is that none of the studies reviewed was carried out on the agricultural sector of Nigeria as a geographic location; this call for serious concern. As a result, this study examined the effect of firm characteristics on corporate cash holding of listed companies in agricultural and consumer goods sector in Nigeria. Consequently, the study sort to bridge the gaps aforementioned above, hence it was a research on the effects of firm characteristics on corporate cash holdings of companies in agricultural and consumer goods sector in Nigeria.

Methodology

3.1 Research Design

Ex-post facto (post event) research design was adopted due to the fact that the study made use of secondary sources of data. The choice of this research design was based on the fact that the study relied on historic accounting data which were obtained from the financial statements and accounts of agricultural and consumer goods companies in Nigeria.

3.2 Area of Study

The research was conducted in Nigeria and among agricultural and consumer goods companies listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX) as at the last trading day of December, 2021.

3.3 Sources of Data

Already existing data from audited and published annual reports and accounts of the sampled companies were used. It covered a period of 2011 to 2021.

3.4 Population of the Study

The population consists of all the five (5) agricultural companies and all the twenty (20) consumer goods companies listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX) as at 31st December 2021.

3.5 Determination of Sample Size

The purposive sampling technic was adopted. This choice made because the researcher wanted to select firms that have at least six years data and above. Given the size of the population, all the five (5) agricultural and fourteen (14) out of the twenty (20) consumer goods companies listed on the platform of Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX) as at 31st December, 2021 were enlisted for the study. While the whole population is made up of 25 companies, the sample is made up of 19 companies which represent 76% of the entire population of the study.

3.6 Model Specification

Multiple regression models (panel least squares) was adopted and specified in line with previous related literature for the purpose of this study. Regression analysis is one of the most common methods used in statistical data analysis. The concept of regression was first founded by Sir Francis Galton in 19th Century. It was adapted from Ugwu et al (2021) who carried out research using related tool. This model was adopted because the study is on effect (effect of firm's characteristics on cash holding of agricultural and consumer goods sectors in Nigeria). Koutsoyiannis (2003) as cited in Inyama (2016), states that model specification involves the determination of the dependent and explanatory variables, were included in the model, the theoretical expectations about the sign and the size of the parameters of the function. The analytical model that was considered for this study encapsulated the chosen elements of firm characteristics which include profitability, capital expenditure, firm size, asset structure and leverage, and corporate cash holding. It is important to note that corporate cash holding was proxied by cash and cash equivalent, while profitability and firm size were represented by profit for the year and total assets, respectively. The models of the study specified in line with the hypotheses of the study were stated as detailed below:

The Models were specified as, and in line with the hypotheses, as shown below:

Thus, for hypothesis one which states that profit for the year does not have significant effect on cash and cash equivalents of firms in agricultural and consumer goods sectors in Nigeria. The hypothesis was modelled as:

$$CCE_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 PFTY_t + \mu \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

For hypothesis two which states that capital expenditure does not have significant effect on cash and cash equivalents of firms in agricultural and consumer goods sectors in Nigeria. The hypothesis was modelled as:

$$CCE_t = \beta_0 + \beta_2 CEXP_t + \mu \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

Where, in our equation, the following acronyms or symbols were used to represent the respective variables and explained thus:

CCE	=	Cash and Cash Equivalents
PFTY	=	Profit for the year (Profitability)
CEXP	=	Capital Expenditure
Bo	=	Constant Term
β_1	=	Coefficient of Profitability
β_2	=	Coefficient of Capital Expenditure
μ	=	Error Term

3.7 Description of Variables in the Model

The research variables which were structured into dependent and independent variables for the purpose of data analysis were described as follows:

Dependent variable

Corporate cash holding: Cash holding was used as a dependent variable in the study which was proxied cash and cash equivalents. Cash holding may be defined as cash at hand, cash in bank and other securities or investments whose maturity period is within six months and are easily convertible or available to be utilized.

Independent variables

Profitability: This is the ability of an entity to generate returns. One of the key objectives of a business is to generate profit. Profitability enables business to survive and expand and further rewards owners. For the purpose of this study, profit for the year was used.

Capital expenditure: Capital expenditure is funds used by a company to acquire, upgrade, and maintain physical productive assets such as property, plant or equipment. This expenditure is incurred in order to increase the capacity or efficiency of the company for more than one accounting period.

3.8 Method of Data Analysis

One of the methods of analysis is the use of regression equation estimated to evaluate the effect of firm's characteristics on corporate cash holding of agricultural and consumer goods sectors in Nigeria. Random panel regression was used to test the hypothesis.

3.8.1 Test Procedure

In arriving at a decision, the following steps were taken:

- i. The hypotheses were restated in null and alternate forms,
- ii. The decision criterion was stated,
- iii. The presentation of the E-view 9.0 result
- iv. The null hypothesis is rejected or accepted based on the decision rule/criterion or criteria.
- v. Conclusion is drawn

3.9 Decision Rule

Accept the null hypothesis (H_0) if the P-value is greater than the calculated A-value ($P\text{-value} > A = 0.05$) and t-statistic < 2 . Otherwise, do not accept.

4.0 Data Analysis

Data analysis depicts how the data collected for each of the company are analyzed with diverse analytical tools.

Results

The hypotheses of the study were tested by applying the result of panel regression analysis carried out. The tests were aided with E-views 9.0 Version. The hypotheses were tested in the following order:

- Re-statement of the hypothesis in both null and alternate.
- Decision rule for rejection of the null hypothesis
- Presentation of the test result.
- Decision.
- Conclusion

4.1. Test of Hypothesis One.

Hypothesis one sought to determine the effect of profit for the year on cash and cash equivalent of firms in agricultural and consumer goods sectors in Nigeria.

Statement of Hypothesis

H₀: Profit for the year does not have significant effect on cash and cash equivalents of firms in agricultural and consumer goods sectors in Nigeria.

H₁: Profit for the year has significant effect on cash and cash equivalents of firms in agricultural and consumer goods sectors in Nigeria.

Decision Rule

Accept the null hypothesis (H₀) if the P-value is greater than the calculated A-value (P-value > = 0.05). Otherwise, do not accept.

Presentation of Test Results

Table 4.1: Test of Hypothesis One

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	5.272968	2.207202	2.388983	0.0207
PFTY	0.061346	0.150452	3.407741	0.0052

Source: Researcher's E-Views 9.0 Output, 2025

From table 4.1 above, it was observed that the probability, P-value of 0.0052 < 0.05 level of significance, (P = 0.0052 < 0.05). It further revealed a positive coefficient (r) = 0.61346 which implies that the explanatory variable (independent variable), profit for the year could explain or account for up to 61% of what happens to the dependent variable, cash and cash equivalents in the estimated equation. Thus, we reject the null hypothesis (H₀) and accept the alternate hypothesis (H₁) accordingly. This decision was reinforced as it was further observed that the value of t-statistics of profit being 3.407741 is greater than 2.0 (t = 3.407741 > 2.0).

Conclusion

We therefore conclude that profit for the year has positive and significant effect on cash and cash equivalents of firms in agricultural and consumer goods sectors in Nigeria, (r = 0.61346; P = 0.0052 < = 0.05; t = 3.407741 > 2.0).

4.2: Test of Hypothesis Two

Hypothesis two sought to ascertain the effect of capital expenditure on cash and cash equivalent of firms in agricultural and consumer goods sectors in Nigeria.

Statement of Hypothesis

H₀: Capital expenditure does not have significant effect on cash and cash equivalents of agricultural and consumer goods firms in Nigeria.

H₁: Capital expenditure has significant effect on cash and cash equivalents of agricultural and consumer goods firms in Nigeria.

Decision Rule

Accept the null hypothesis (H₀) if the P-value is greater than the calculated A-value (P-value > A = 0.05). Otherwise, do not accept.

Presentation of Test Results

Table 4.2: Test of Hypothesis Two

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	5.272968	2.207202	2.388983	0.0207
CEXP	0.115649	0.160797	2.719229	0.0453

Source: Researcher's E-Views 9.0 Output, 2025

Decision

From table 4.2 above, it was observed that the capital expenditure has a P-value of $0.0453 < 0.05$ level of significance, ($r = 0.115649$; $P = 0.0453 < A = 0.05$; $t = 2.719229 > 2.0$). Thus, we reject the null hypothesis (H₀) and accept the alternate hypothesis (H₁) accordingly. This decision was strengthened by the observation that the value of t-statistics of capital expenditure being 2.719229 is greater than 2.0, ($t = 2.719229 > 2.0$).

Conclusion

We therefore conclude that capital expenditure has positive and significant effect on cash and cash equivalents of firms in agricultural and consumer goods sector in Nigeria, ($r = 0.115649$; $P = 0.0453 < A = 0.05$; $t = 2.719229 > 2.0$).

4.3 Discussion of Findings

4.3.1 Profitability and Cash holding

Hypothesis one states that profit for the year does not have significant effect on cash and cash equivalents of firms in agricultural and consumer goods sectors in Nigeria. From the regression analysis result obtained in table 4.2.1, the study found that profit for the year has positive and significant effect on the cash and cash equivalence of firms in agricultural and consumer goods sector in Nigeria. The result as obtained on table 4.3.1 reveals a positive coefficient ($r = 0.61346$). It also reveals a probability P-value of 0.0052 which is found to be less than the A-value of 0.05 level of significance, ($P = 0.0052 < 0.05$). Based on the above finding, the null hypothesis (H₀) was rejected while the alternate hypothesis (H₁) was accepted accordingly. This decision was reinforced as it was further observed that the value of t-statistics of profit for the year being 3.407741 is greater than 2.0 ($t = 3.407741 > 2.0$). It was concluded that profit for the year has positive and significant effect on cash and cash equivalents of firms in agricultural and consumer goods sectors in Nigeria. The implication of the finding is that

if firms in agricultural and consumer goods sectors in Nigeria make more profits, there will be the likelihood of having more cash holdings. In other words, every unit increase in profit triggers an increase in cash and cash equivalents of a firm. This enhances the chances of funding activities of the firms first, through internal sources. The above is in line with one of the major positions of the pecking order theory of Myers and Majluf (1984) who opine that financing comes from three sources, internal funds, debt and new equity. The theory suggests that companies prioritize their sources of financing, first preferring internal financing, and then debt, lastly raising equity as a last resort. Hence, internal financing is used first; when that is depleted, then debt is issued; and when it is no longer sensible to issue any more debt, equity is issued. It proposed that the more firms remain profitable, the more it will finance investments with its retained earnings. The above finding is also in line with the findings of Cheryta, *et al.* (2017), Tahir, *et al* (2016), Boric and Kruja (2016), Abushammala and Sulaiman (2014), Wang (2014), Bokpin (2013), Ziu-ul-hanna and Asghar (2013), Ogundipe, *et al* (2012), Benjamin and Samuel (2012), Rizwan and Javed (2011), Drobetz and Grüninger (2007) and Xin and Xu (2006). Their studies on cash holdings revealed that profitability was positive and had significant effect on cash holdings of firms in Albania, Jordan, Karachi and Ghana, respectively.

4.3.2 Capital expenditure and Cash holding

Hypothesis two states that capital expenditure does not have significant effect on cash and cash equivalents of firm in agricultural and consumer goods sectors in Nigeria. Result of the regression analysis shows that capital expenditure has a positive and significant effect on the cash holdings of firms in agricultural and consumer goods sectors in Nigeria. From table 4.3.2 above, it was observed that the capital expenditure has a positive coefficient ($r = 0.115649$). It also reveals a probability P-value of $0.0453 < 0.05$ level of significance, ($P = 0.0453 < 0.05$). It was further observed that the value of t-statistics of capital expenditure being 2.719229 is greater than 2.0, ($t = 2.719229 > 2.0$). Following the set decision rule for the study, the null hypothesis (H_0) was rejected and the alternate hypothesis (H_1) accepted accordingly. Consequently, it was concluded that capital expenditure has significant effect on cash and cash equivalents of firms in agricultural and consumer goods sectors in Nigeria.

The implication of this finding is that an increase in capital expenditure on projects with positive net present values will lead to increase in cash holding of firms in agricultural and consumer goods sectors in Nigeria. Increased investment in capital projects could lead to increase in production capacity which may trigger more inflow and subsequently trigger increase in cash holding. The above is in line with one of the major postulations of the pecking order theory of Myers and Majluf (1984) which states that financing comes from three sources, internal funds, debt and new equity. The theory suggests that companies prioritize their sources of financing, first preferring internal financing, and then debt, lastly raising equity as a last resort.

The finding of this study also aligns with the findings of Chireka and Fakoye (2017), Maximilian (2015), Kafayat, *et al* (2014), Islam (2012), Ogundipe, *et al* (2012) and Bates, *et al* (2009). Their studies on firm's cash holdings carried out across South Africa, Pakistan, United States and Nigerian industrial goods sectors respectively, reveal that capital expenditure was positive and had significant effect on corporate cash holdings.

5.0 Summary of Findings, Conclusion and Recommendations

5.1 Summary of Findings

1. Profit for the year has positive and significant effect on cash and cash equivalents of firms in agricultural and consumer goods sectors in Nigeria, ($r = 0.61346$; $P = 0.0052 < 0.05$; $t = 3.407741 > 2.0$).
2. Capital expenditure has positive and significant effect on cash and cash equivalents of firms in agricultural and consumer goods sectors in Nigeria, ($r = 0.115649$; $P = 0.0453 < 0.05$; $t = 2.719229 > 2.0$).

5.2 Conclusion

The study examined the effect of firm's characteristics on corporate cash holding of agricultural and consumer goods sectors in Nigeria from 2011 to 2021. A sample of all the five agricultural firms and fourteen consumer goods firms listed on the Nigeria exchange group for the period was selected for the work. Data analysis was empirically done using a cross sectional regression analysis (otherwise referred to as panel least squares) of the effect of firm characteristics (profit for the year, capital expenditure, on cash and cash equivalents of firms in agricultural and consumer goods sectors in Nigeria. The study found that profit for the year; capital expenditure, firm size and asset structure have positive and significant effect on cash and cash equivalents of firms in agricultural and consumer goods sectors in Nigeria from 2011 to 2021. While leverage has negative and non-significant effect on cash and cash equivalent of firms in agricultural and consumer goods sectors in Nigeria. The Adjusted R-Squared (R^2) indicates that 68% of the changes in cash and cash equivalents (corporate cash holding) are accounted for by the explanatory variables (firm characteristics). The study concluded that profit for the year; capital expenditure, firm size and asset structure are good predictors of cash and cash equivalents (corporate cash holding) of firms in agricultural and consumer goods sectors in Nigeria from 2011 to 2021. This implies that for firms in agricultural and consumer goods sectors in Nigeria to hold cash optimally there would need to effectively manage profitability, capital investment decisions, investment in assets and expansionary programs, and strategically invest in property, plant and equipment, while keeping leverage at moderation.

5.3 Recommendations

In line with the findings made and the conclusion drawn, the following were recommended:

1. Managers of firms in agricultural and consumer goods sectors in Nigeria should engage optimally, all activities that will generate more profit for the year so as to increase cash holding firms in agricultural and consumer goods sectors in Nigeria. This is because, cash and cash equivalents which is the proxy for corporate cash holding increases with increase in profit for the year, hence profit for the year has positive and significant effect on cash and cash equivalent. This could be achieved through aggressive marketing and promotion as well as increased sales outlets and cheaper means of transportation for deliveries.
2. Management of firms in agricultural and consumer goods sectors in Nigeria should thoroughly evaluate capital expenditure taking into account, economy, efficiency and effectiveness before embracing any. This will help to guarantee optimal return and increase cash and cash equivalents of firms in agricultural and consumer goods sectors in Nigeria. This can be achieved through effective governance for better strategic choices, by carrying out cost benefit analysis and by use of competent labour for implementation.

5.4 Contribution to Knowledge

When effect of firm characteristics on corporate cash holding of agricultural and consumer goods sectors in Nigeria is in focus, it is often observed that there is paucity of research works examining this phenomenon. This could be attributed to why, to the best of knowledge of the researcher, none of the reviewed related studies was

carried out on agricultural sector. The study was conceived to solve this problem. This goal was met as the study contributes to the existing body of knowledge by further reducing dearth of literature on the effect of corporate characteristics on corporate cash holding and by adding empirical evidence from the firms in agricultural and consumer goods sectors in Nigeria into the on-going discussion of effects of firm characteristics on corporate cash holdings as a global issue.

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